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THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE DESIGN TASTE

- JAPAN, SOUTH KOREA AND FINLAND -

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ABSTRACT

This research compares design taste internationally. The countries which compare are Japan, South Korea, and Finland. It is the purpose to consider the difference in the design taste which the culture of east and west brings about.

In order to investigate the taste of a design, the pattern was used in this research. Furthermore, the purchase factor was investigated in this research. The result of investigation was interesting. It is that the tendency for Japan to differ was shown, although South Korea and Finland were similar. For example, in Japan, purchase factors were a price and a color, in South Korea and Finland were the function and form. These are considered to be the results which cannot be explained only by the conventional geographical and cultural factor..

Keywords: design taste, culture trait, traditional pattern

INTRODUCTION

Due to the fast-evolving technological innovations, manufacturers that have achieved high quality and high functionality are now forced to shift their strategy unprecedentedly. It is a movement called demolition innovation and once consumer satisfaction meets the function and quality, they do not want anything better, however, cheaper prices and a range of colours and designs are more important factors for the product purchase. On the other hand, globalization progresses and many companies are pressed for entry to a world market. However, is a domestic market-oriented product able to sell at an oversea market?

Should not a product be made in consideration of the taste or culture of the consumer of each country? Of course, there is also a case where the standardized product is sold at a world market as it is like Coca-Cola or Nike.

In the case of product development, what should be standardized, what must be made and changed by a country? In this research, we do a focus to a design attribute and explore the common characteristic and originality of design taste of each country.

RECENT RESEARCH

APPROACH FROM THE DIFFERENCE IN CULTURE

The difference in the human characteristic by the difference in culture is studied for many years. For example, Westerners tend to focus on objects, whereas East Asians tend to focus more on contexts, relationships, and background (Chua, Boland, & Nisbett, 2005; Nisbett & Miyamoto, 2005). Thus, the difference between the East and the West is directed in various domains. This is being able to say also about taste. Since Japan, South Korea, and China are located in the same East, there is a common tendency to like white and blue. Many international comparisons about a color are studied especially. It is said that the taste to man's color is formed from infancy, and tends to be affected from nature or society.

Also many researches on the taste of a design exist. It is almost the case which is investigated about the color and form which are attributes. However, various results are drawn by the object and area to compare. Yasui (2000) indicates that Japanese people like a straight line design and South Koreans like a curve.

As such, there is research as which a difference is regarded by design taste in the countries in East Asia.

FORMATION OF GOOD WILL

What kind of point becomes a conclusive factor in the taste to a design?

The factor which determines taste can be divided into an external factor and an internal factor. An external factor has the symmetry (Mealey et al., 1999; Grammer et al., 1994) of a stimulus, a type (Winkielman et al., 2006), and complexity (Rentschler et al., 1999).

On the other hand, an internal factor has training experience (Wiston & Cupchik, 1992) of the personality characteristic (Furnhan&Walker, 2001; Eysenck, 1972) and art capability, and a functional difference (Levy, 1976) of a cerebral hemisphere. Since research is complicated this time, a focus is carried out only to an external factor.

Thus, it is thought that many factors are concerned with good will judgment. Since the research on taste formation is a complicated thing in which many factors are intermingled, various results exist. However, the stout effect by which the repetition check is carried out exists. It is mere exposure effect which is a theme of the domain of psychology (Zajonc, 1968). People take to it by seeing

repeatedly. It seems that the environment which lives is important if it thinks so. This effect is reported in various stimuli or culture.

MEANING OF A PATTERN

The pattern made applicable to investigation can be interpreted as having drawn a formal combination on the plane. Natural breathing and beauty are expressed by the Even if it sees historically, the feature of culture appears in patterns, such as Assyria, Persia, Greece, Rome, Byzantine one, Romanesque, and Gothic, from the Egypt pattern which is a root of Western culture pattern (Mitsui 2000) . The design is changing from the simple geometrical form to what used the animal and the plant as the motif.

Since Japan has a change every season, a pattern has many with which nature was described. The pattern of Europe has many geometry things and things of symmetry.

Since the original interpretation of each country is added while having universality, when a pattern explores the starting point of a design, it can be called interesting material.

Kamijo (1981) says that the pattern symbolizes religious and economical and political activity of a time.

- A. Vegetable pattern
- B. Finland pattern
- C. Polygon pattern
- D. Stripes and lattice pattern
- E. Japanese pattern
- F. circle and curvilinear pattern

Figure 1. 30 patterns used for investigation .They are roughly classified into six according to the motif. Furthermore, it elected five typical things each. A material is extracted from various pattern dictionaries.

METHODS

There are some investigations about the consumer preference of design. Investigation was conducted in the following procedures.

Survey1(Pre investigation):

First, we conducted pre investigation in order to select the pattern used for investigation from many patterns. There are four classifications of a pattern, motif, semantic classification, the classification by a mathematical group theory, the classification using a layer concept. In this research, the motif classification was adopted and 50 typical things were chosen. The typical patterns are extracted from databases of many patterns. It adapted the classic example from the viewpoint of formal principles, such as harmony, contrast, a promotion, symmetry, and balance, and the composition of Dondis (1973), and elected 50 patterns.

The elected pattern of 50 sheets was classified into the student of China and South Korea according to the fixed standard, and was narrowed down to 22 sheets (March, 2009, a subject: Five Chinese college students, six South Korean college students Also any local enforcement). Choice variables are a favorite thing, a disagreeable thing, a thing of the China image, a thing of the South Korean image, and a thing of a Japanese image. Investigation is as follows.

Outline

Enforcement period: February- April, 2010

Subject: 153 China, 101 South Korea, and 91 Japan carry all out there.

Method: Questionnaire investigation

The result of pre investigation

The following things were shown by pre investigation. The favorite pattern showed the tendency which China and South Korea resembled. The pattern which hates Japan and South Korea was similar. In addition, both countries tended to like the vegetable pattern. When the practical use to the product of a pattern was heard, China could be applied to all the product categories, Japan and South Korea were not accepted in almost all domains.

Based on this pre investigation, we decided to carry out main enumeration.

Since the taste of China and South Korea was alike, in main enumeration, China was removed and made South Korea, Japan, and Finland applicable to investigation.

Survey2(Main enumeration):

The reason for making Finland applicable to investigation is as follows.

Finland is located in a European vestibule leading to the outside. Therefore, Finland is in Asia and the symmetrical Europe culture, and the design is presenting the interim aspect of east and west. Furthermore, we performed comparison with Europe. In order to investigate the characteristic of Asia, comparison with Finland is also performed.

Tasks

The pattern used for main enumeration was chosen based on the typical category for the selection criteria of pre investigation. A typical category is six, A. vegetable pattern, B. Finland pattern, C. polygon pattern, D. stripes and a lattice pattern, E. Japan pattern, and F. circle and a curvilinear pattern. It prepared five points at a time a total of 30 points respectively.

The contents of questions are to choose a favorite thing and an oriental, West thing every group. It investigates by three nations and the common characteristic and originality are explored. How much do a design like the pattern, i.e., a color, and a form influence purchase? How does it change with countries? To clarify them, investigation about the purchase factor was also conducted.

We examined the standard which understands a product category. As shown in Fig. 2, the standard was denoted by the matrix of two axes and the applied product was plotted. That it is public shows the product used in public and private used in the room.

The products that are high participation and public things are a cellular phone and clothes. High participation and private are home electronics, low participation and public is stationery, low participation and private is Mug. The variable set up a color, a function, a form, a price, ease of use, and a material.

Outline

Figure 2. Product category classification matrix.

Figure 3. Three-nation comparison of a favorite pattern and a disagreeable pattern

Enforcement period: August, 2010 - October
 Subject: 69 Finland, 117South Korea, 61Japan

Analysis

The preference survey of a pattern makes a subject choose applicable top three. They were made into mark and the whole has been grasped by making a selected ratio into a graph. Next, we conduct Chi square test for goodness of fit and residual analysis in order to compare for three countries.

We perform ranking attachment of a variable also about a purchase factor, and compute the weight of each variable by a score.

RESULTS

By this investigation, we were able to obtain the very interesting result.

PATTERN TASTE

The data of a favorite pattern and a disagreeable pattern was made into the graph, and the tendency of Japan, South Korea, and Finland was seen. The most favorite thing and the most disagreeable thing are as being shown in Fig. 3. About the favorite

Figure 4. All the comparison of a favorite pattern and a disagreeable pattern. T An upper left graph is what compared three nations of a favorite pattern. An upper right graph is what compared three nations of a disagreeable pattern. A lower left graph is what compared South Korea and Finland of the favorite pattern. A lower right graph is what compared South Korea and Finland of the disagreeable pattern.

Table1. The result to which the upper table conducted residual analysis of the three nations of a favorite pattern. The result to which the lower table conducted residual analysis of the three nations of a disagreeable pattern.

		A 71.033**					B 30.281**				
JAPAN		4.9	-3.6	1.5	-0.9	--4.4	4.0	-2.8	-2.6	-0.2	0.9
SOUTH KOREA		-1.5	-0.4	-0.9	2.9	0.2	-0.5	0	0.4	1.1	-0.7
FINLAND		-3.8	4.6	-0.6	-2.3	4.7	-3.3	2.7	2.1	-1.1	-0.1
		C 31.885**					D 7.005				
JAPAN		-0.2	-0.6	4.2	0.1	-3.7	-0.5	0.2	0.3	-1.3	0.3
SOUTH KOREA		-0.4	1.4	-1.9	0.7	0	-0.1	-1.1	-1.4	0.7	1.3
FINLAND		0.5	-1.0	-1.8	-0.8	3.5	-0.4	1.1	1.3	0.4	-1.8
		E 32.606**					F 48.577**				
JAPAN		-1.6	1.4	1.3	-3.6	3.0	-2.1	-0.4	-1.7	4.9	-1.7
SOUTH KOREA		-1.6	-0.6	-0.3	3.5	-1.1	3.1	-1.7	-1.9	-0.8	2.3
FINLAND		3.3	-0.7	-0.9	-0.4	-1.6	-1.4	2.3	3.8	-3.8	-1.0
		A 44.342					B 36.729				
JAPAN		-0.9	0.3	-2.6	-1.7	3.9	-3.3	0.7	2.4	0	-0.5
SOUTH KOREA		-1.0	3.1	-1.6	0	-1.8	-1.1	-0.1	-0.5	2.6	-1.6
FINLAND		2.0	-3.7	4.2	1.6	-1.8	4.4	-0.6	-1.7	-2.9	2.2
		C 35.229**					D 11.378				
JAPAN		1.6	-1.4	-1.0	-3.0	3.5	-0.9	0.8	0.5	-0.3	-0.4
SOUTH KOREA		0.8	-2.1	0	2.0	-0.9	-1.3	1.1	1.0	-1.0	0
FINLAND		-2.4	3.7	1.0	0.7	-2.3	2.3	-2.0	-1.6	1.5	0.4
		E 56.682**					F 25.593**				
JAPAN		-0.2	-1.3	-2.3	6.8	-3.9	3.1	-0.1	-1.0	-1.5	-1.1
SOUTH KOREA		1.8	1.6	0	-4.0	1.7	-3.8	-0.8	3.0	2.3	0.3
FINLAND		-1.8	-0.6	2.2	-2.1	1.9	1.2	1.0	-2.3	-1.1	0.8

pattern, Japan chose the check handle, South Korea chose the plant, and Finland chose the circle. The

disagreeable pattern which South Korea chose was chosen from the genre of the same vegetable pattern.

Table 2. Image comparison of the West and the East of a pattern

	West			East			
JAPAN							
SOUTH KOREA	+	+	-	-	-	-	+
	-	-	+	+	+	+	-

	West		East	
JAPAN				
FINLAND	+	+	-	-
	-	-	+	+

Next, we have grasped the whole tendency from the graph. The upper 2 sheet graph of Fig. 4 shows the selected ratio of a favorite pattern and a disagreeable pattern. In each country, except for polygon pattern of C, and Japanese pattern of E, palatability had appeared clearly.

In addition, the graph shows that Japan's change is sharp. Then, it is the lower 2 sheet of Fig. 4 which created the graph except for Japanese data. These graphs show that South Korea and Finland have the similar palatability.

In order that we might investigate whether it is statistically meaningful in these, we computed the value the Chi square and conducted residual analysis. The pattern which likes the upper table of Table 1, and the following table show the disagreeable pattern. When a favorite pattern is analyzed according to a pattern, it was vegetable pattern of A ($\chi^2=71.033, p<.001$), Finland pattern of B ($\chi^2=30.281, p<.001$), polygon pattern of C ($\chi^2=31.885, p<.001$), Japan pattern of E ($\chi^2=32.606, p<.001$), circle and a curvilinear pattern of F ($\chi^2=48.577, p<.001$) that there is a difference in three countries. Similarly, it was C ($\chi^2=35.229, p<.001$), E ($\chi^2=56.682, p<.001$), and F ($\chi^2=25.593, p<.001$) that a disagreeable pattern has a difference.

Furthermore, it was investigated how each country would have caught the image of east and west. When Japan in the East was compared with Finland in the

West, the circle pattern was Japan's West image, but it turned out that it is the recognition from which Finland is not so and a pattern oriental in Finland is different in Japan. The pattern of a check has been recognized to be the West in Japan, and to be the East in South Korea. Although it was an arabesque pattern of the oriental image, in South Korea, it has been recognized as the East, and has been recognized as the West in Japan.

PURCHASE FACTOR

The design investigated how much it would be thought as important at the time of purchase. The graph on Fig. 5 has totaled Japanese data. Every product category has the tendency to think a price as important. Moreover, as for clothes, it is the feature that, as for a material, furniture, or a mug, a color influences. About a cellular phone, It turns out that it has influenced with sufficient balance of all the factors.

In South Korea, a form, a function, and a color are thought as important on the whole. Like Japan, the price is not conscious and low participation products tend to ask for ease of use.

Also in Finland, the function and the form are thought as important. Especially a form is thought as important in furniture and clothes.

It was shown that South Korea resembles Finland rather than Japan. This was able to say the same thing also by the pattern.

DISCUSSION

We are having conducted this investigation and were able to derive some interesting knowledge. The unexpected result of precedence research was drawn about the taste of a pattern. That is, although the composition of the East and the West, i.e., Japan and South Korea versus Finland, was able to be considered, the similar result came out in South Korea and Finland. In addition, since tastes have appeared in Japanese data clearly, Japanese people are considered that sensitivity has ripened.

Figure 5. Purchase factor comparison according to product category

The similarity of each country is that favorite patterns are a striped pattern and a vegetable pattern. However, the favorite thing and the disagreeable thing are intermingled also in a vegetable pattern, and the possibility of complexity or symmetry is suggested to the standard of palatability.

Moreover, we conducted investigation which explores the product category by which a design like a pattern influences purchase. We were able to obtain the useful result also in this investigation. South Korea and Finland were similar like the case of

a pattern. It seems that the consumer characteristics of two countries are alike.

These are considered to be the results which cannot be explained only by the conventional geographical and cultural factor. What kind of factor has influenced? We are going to investigate the factor which will explain the palatability of a design from now on in more detail.

REFERENCES

Chua, H.F., Boland, J.E. & Nisbett, R.E. (2005) Cultural variation in eye movements during scene perception. *Proceeding of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 102(35), 12629-12633

- Donis A. Dondis: A Primer of Visual Literacy, MIT Press, (1973)
 (Lan Luo, P.K. Kannan, and Brian T. Ratchford: Incorporating Subjective Characteristics in Product Design and Evaluations, *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 15, (2008) pp. 182-194
- Eysenck, H.J. (1972). Personal Preferences and Individual Differences. In D. O'Hare (Ed), *Psychology and arts*. Harvester Press.
- Furnham, A., & Walker, J. (2001). Personality and judgements of abstract, pop art and representational paintings. *European Journal of Personality*, 15, 57-72
- Levy, J. (1976). Lateral dominance and aesthetic preference. *Neuropsychologia*, 14, 431-445
- Mealy, L., Bridgestock, R. & Townsend, G.C. (1999) Symmetry and perceived facial attractiveness. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 76, 151-158
- Nisbett, R.E. & Miyamoto, Y. (2005). The influence of culture: Holistic versus analytic perception. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 9(10), 467-473
- Rentschler, I., Jolter, M., Unzicker, A., & Landis, T. (1999) Innate and learned components of human visual preference. *Current Biology*, Vol. 9, 665-671
- Winkielman, P., Halberstadt, J., Fazen. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, Vol. 76, 151-158
- Winston, A.S., & Cupchik, G.C. (1992). The evaluation of high art and popular art by native and experienced viewers. *Visual Arts Research*, 18, 1-14
- Yasui, H. (2000). Comparison of the South Korean culture and a design, and Japanese culture and a design, *Design Study Research*, Vol. 46, No.5, 51-58
- Zajonc, R.B. (1968). Attitudinal effects of mere exposure. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 9, 1-27